

Università degli Studi 'G.d'Annunzio', Chieti
Facoltà di Lettere e Filosofia
Dipartimento di Scienze dell'Antichità

SOMA 2005

Proceedings of the IX Symposium
on Mediterranean Archaeology,
Chieti (Italy), 24-26 February 2005

Edited by

O. Menozzi, M. L. Di Marzio
and D. Fossataro

Introduction by S. Trinchese

Preliminary editing by L. Cherstich

Castel Manfrino excavation edited by S. Antonelli

BAR International Series 1739
2008

This title published by

Archaeopress
Publishers of British Archaeological Reports
Gordon House
276 Banbury Road
Oxford OX2 7ED
England
bar@archaeopress.com
www.archaeopress.com

BAR S1739

*SOMA 2005. Proceedings of the IX Symposium on Mediterranean Archaeology, Chieti (Italy),
24-26 February 2005*

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Logo drawing by E. di Valerio

ISBN 978 1 4073 0181 5

Printed in England by Butler and Tanner

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Oxford
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The Bath-Gymnasium Complex of Vedius in Ephesus

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Within the last four years the history, the architecture, the furnishings and the decoration of the Vedius Gymnasium in Ephesus have been profoundly investigated by a team of archaeologists and architects. After this period of intensive research the history of the Imperial bath-gymnasium-complex can now be largely determined. The different phases of the building can mainly be divided into a first major phase in the middle of the 2nd century A.D. (time of construction), a second major phase in the first quarter of the 5th century, the end of the buildings's function as a bath in the second half of the 5th century, a systematic robbing of the furnishings and the decoration of the monument at the end of the 5th century, processes of destruction in the 6th century and last traces of use in the middle of the 7th century A.D. The history of the same area before the construction of the baths goes back to Late-Geometric times (middle of 8th century B.C.).

The presented chronology of the Vedius Gymnasium serves as a basis for any further interpretations, which will be complemented by the conceived investigations on the prehistory of the area.

Introduction

Between the end of the 1st and the middle of the 2nd century A.D. four so-called bath-gymnasium-complexes were built in the city of Ephesus: the Harbour, the East, the Theatre and the Vedius Gymnasia (Fig. 1). Laid out symmetrically along a longitudinal axis, they serve as the 'ideal type' of a bath-gymnasium in Roman Imperial Asia Minor. Characteristic of this type of building is the combination of a Roman bath – variations of the Imperial type – with the Greek *gymnasion*.¹

Since the summer of 2000, the Vedius Gymnasium, a bath-gymnasium-complex founded by Publius Vedius Antoninus² on the north-west slope of the Panayırdağ and consecrated in the mid-2nd century A.D., has become a focus of interest for Austrian research activities in Ephesus (Fig. 2).

Along with the resumption of earlier research on the Vedius Gymnasium carried out by M. Theuer and F. Miltner in the 1920s and 1950s,³ all previous and current investigations will be incorporated in the final publication. The current project includes not only a theoretical reconstruction of the structure together with its furnishings and decoration, and an explanation of the technical aspects of the baths, but also an archaeological-historical interpretation of the area. This will shed light on the history of the baths, the function of the building after the baths were no longer in use, and the history of the area before the construction of the baths as an aspect of the general history of the city of Ephesus. M. La Torre from the University of Applied Studies in Wiesbaden is responsible for the building analysis and will publish his results in a separate volume.⁴

Fieldwork

To make an outline of the history of the building, and to determine the layout of the ground plan and exterior views and the circumstances of its destruction, 12 areas inside the monument have been investigated archaeologically during the last four years (Fig. 3). By virtue of possessing two versions of the donor's dedication we already knew the initial point of this chronology at the beginning of our campaign: From the reference to the proconsulate of Lucius Antonius Albus in the province of Asia, the inauguration of the building can be dated to the years 147 – 149 A.D., that is, during the reign of Antoninus Pius.⁵ The epigraphically determined construction period also offers a good opportunity for research in Roman ceramics to study the first appearance of particular wares and shapes in this geographic area. In this context, we should especially mention the Eastern Sigillata B, whose definite morphological development from Flavian until Severian times is still largely unknown.⁶

In 2001, a 17 by 20 m large trench was excavated in the H-shaped *basilica thermarum* of the building, which functioned as *ambulacrum* or *ambulatio*. The goal was to discover the date and the cause of destruction of the baths.

In the stratigraphically oldest finds, we were able to discern elements of the original decoration from the middle of the 2nd century A.D. The partially preserved, geometrically decorated mosaic with a chessboard-pattern and an hourglass-motif represents the level of the first phase. A marble pavement is part of a later or second phase of decoration, assigned to the first quarter of the 5th century A.D. The chronological classification is primarily based on Late Roman-C-cups of type 3/small variation, LRC-plates of type 1/late variation, and fragments of amphorae of type L.R. 3.⁷

¹ Yegül 1992: 250-313; Nielsen 1993: 104-8; Farrington 1987: 50-9; Maccanico 1963: 32-60; Fasolo 1962: 31-40; Steskal 2003: 227-39.

² Steskal 2001: 177-88; Kalinowski 2002: 109-49.

³ Keil 1929a: 20-45; Keil 1929b: 21-33; Keil 1930: 17-20; Miltner 1955: 23-6; Steskal and La Torre 2001: 223-46.

⁴ La Torre forthcoming.

⁵ Steskal 2001: 177-88.

⁶ Steskal and Ladstätter 2004 forthcoming.

⁷ Steskal and Ladstätter 2004 forthcoming.

The secondary *opus sectile* of the so-called ‘Kaisersaal’ – the Imperial hall – also forms part of this second major phase in the first quarter of the 5th century A.D. (Fig. 4):

Due to a considerable weakness in the construction, the foundation of the room started to sink in the course of time, causing the original *opus sectile* needed to be repaired: For the installation of the secondary floor on the same level as the original one, a levelling-layer needed to be applied. In this layer we found several fragments of statues which had originally belonged to the so-called ‘Kaisersaal’ and that had been placed in the *intercolumnia* of the two-storeyed columnar facade. They had been probably destroyed earlier by an earthquake.

Only the intentionally smashed heads and extremities of the fragmentary statues were used in this layer; the missing torsoes were partly embedded in walls – a phenomenon that was verified by the discovery of a *torso* of an Aphrodite in the north-wall of the *palaestra*. The statues that were only slightly damaged were left in their original places or set up again in the *intercolumnia*. Today this series of exceptional sculptures, discovered in the earlier excavations, is exhibited in the archaeological museums of Izmir and Istanbul.⁸ J. Auinger from Vienna is currently working on the sculptural program of the Vedius Gymnasium and will publish her results in a separate volume.⁹

At the same time the *stoa* of the *palaestra* was decorated with new polychrome mosaics.

The condition of the substructures of the building confirmed its continuous use as a bath after its remodelling in the first quarter of the 5th century. In room N we documented a massive layer of charcoal, which places the last period of use of the baths in the second half of the 5th century. The charcoal is the result of the final processes of heating.

Just before the beginning of the 6th century, the building was systematically robbed of its decoration. By then, the remains of the marble-revetment and the marble-pavement were only scarce.

At the same time the cellars – particularly their sewers – were used to deposit garbage, such as waste food, lamps, vessels made of glass or ceramics, architectural fragments, etc. These cellars were probably used until well into the 6th century.

In the first half of the 6th century A.D., the Vedius Gymnasium was substantially damaged by a devastating fire. Traces of this massive conflagration can be observed in the *basilica thermarum*, the *natatio*, the *frigidarium*, the *caldarium* and in the area of the *propylon*.

In the course of the second half of the 6th century, the vaults of the ceilings collapsed as a separate incident,

caused either by damage of the building fabric due to the fire or by an earthquake at the same time.

The different phases of the Vedius Gymnasium can therefore be summarized in the following manner:¹⁰

- Inauguration of the building (first major phase): between 147 and 149 A.D.
- Second major phase: first quarter of the 5th century A.D.
- End of building’s function as a bath: second half of the 5th century A.D.
- Systematic robbing of the furnishings and the decoration of the building: end of the 5th century A.D.
- Burnt destruction of the building: first half of the 6th century A.D.
- Collapse of the roofs: second half of the 6th century A.D.
- Last traces of use: middle of the 7th century A.D.

Interpretation

The remodelling of the Vedius Gymnasium in the first quarter of the 5th century A.D. is part of a significant rise in building-activities in the area of Ephesus, which began in the middle of the 4th century. Although we are dealing primarily with rebuilding activities and revitalizations and not new buildings, we may assume a minimum of economic prosperity in that time. It seems that the city finally started to recover from the devastating earthquake of 262. Examples of these building activities we may cite are the construction of the *thermae Constantianarum* under Constantius II., the embellishment of the Arcadiane, the renovation of the Varius Bath financed by Scholastica, and several works along the Curetes Street, in the State Agora or in the area of the later Church of Mary. All of these activities established the necessary preconditions for the organization and celebration of the 3rd ecumenical council in June 431 in Ephesus.¹¹

Concerning the function of the different rooms of the Vedius Gymnasium it has to be pointed out, that all of the different interpretations of the various parts of the structure offer just a snap-shot of their contemporary environment.¹² The interpretation of the function of the so-called Kaisersaal, for instance, as a room for the Imperial cult seems – at the time of the construction of the building at least – reasonable, whereas in the 5th century such a function has to be ruled out. Single, exclusive explanations cannot be sustained in this context. The Imperial halls of the Ephesian bath-gymnasia have to be interpreted – at least at the time of their construction – as multi-functional rooms that especially exalted the status of the benefactors. In addition, these rooms functioned as areas of display, in

¹⁰ Steskal and Ladstätter 2004 forthcoming.

¹¹ Thür 1999: 104-20; Thür 2003: 259-73; Bauer 1996: 269-99; Foss 1979: 46-95; Harreither 2002: 78-94; Karwiese 1999: 81-5; Steskal and Ladstätter forthcoming.

¹² Steskal forthcoming.

⁸ Manderscheid 1981: 88-91.

⁹ Auinger 2003: 15-19.

which to hold assemblies, as club houses, and maybe also for the practice of the Imperial cult.¹³

The special ground plan of this kind of building, characterized by axial-symmetry and the combination of a bath with a *palaestra*, is found mainly in western Asia Minor and in the 2nd century A.D. Within the structure of the building there's a significant development from a plan based on a double row of spaces, as in the Harbour Gymnasium at Ephesus and the Hadrianic Baths at Aphrodisias, to a plan with U-shaped halls and reverse circulation pattern, as in the Theatre and the East Gymnasia at Ephesus, and finally to a third type, in which the bath block and the *palaestra* are linked on the same major axis, as in the Vedius Gymnasium or the bath-gymnasium in Sardis.¹⁴

While we can establish a continuous use of the bathing facilities well into Late Antiquity, the function of the *palaestra* seems to change in the same way that sports activities decline in comparison to intellectual ones. There are several reasons for that phenomenon, which I have already discussed in an article in the "Jahreshefte" of the Austrian Archaeological Institute.¹⁵

The reason for the existence of this particular type of building only in the 2nd century A.D. is to a lesser extent due to economic problems that arise in the 3rd century than to a more pragmatic cause: In the case of Ephesus there was simply no need to build a fifth bath-gymnasium of that size.

Another main focus of the current studies is to document the history of the same area before the construction of the baths. A first important step was taken in an excavation on the east side of the *palaestra* in the summer of 2002.¹⁶

In the mixed, nearly 5-m-deep fill of the excavation trench, we discovered small finds, which go back to Late-Geometric times, that is, the 2nd half of the 8th century B.C. Due to ergonomic considerations, we have to assume that the filling-material needed for the levelling of the area in the course of the construction of the Vedius Gymnasium originated from the immediate vicinity. Aside from the finds in the 1920s made by J. Keil and the associated literary evidence, we now have a further indication of a very early use of this area.¹⁷ The finds of the Late-Geometric era are the earliest traces of settlement in the area of the Hellenistic-Roman city of Ephesus.

Conclusions

With this short contribution to this conference I intended to give an overview of our current research on the Vedius Gymnasium. At the end I want to point out again:

The Ephesian bath-gymnasium-complexes were used multi-functionally as places of intellectual and physical training, for conferences and lectures, for social and religious activities and – of course – for body care. The blending of Greek and Roman traditions in these centers of public life, which also served as vehicles for the display of patronage, offer us a vivid impression of everyday life in one of the capitals of the Roman Empire.

Apart from new topographical and urbanistic aspects, the architectural blending of the Roman and Greek cultural heritage, which can hardly be demonstrated more impressively than in the Imperial bath-gymnasia, offers us far-reaching insights to "processes of acculturation", "Romanization", "provincial culture", "the Imperial cult", the system of "benefaction", "recreational activities", and "bathing culture".

The presented chronology is giving us the ability to discuss these phenomena in detail and serves as a basis for any further interpretations.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank the director of the Austrian Archaeological Institute and the excavations in Ephesus, Mr. F. Krinzing, whose support has always been of great value during these works. For substantial contributions to this research I am particularly grateful to M. La Torre, S. Ladstätter, J. Auinger, M. Kerschner and V. Scheibelreiter.

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¹³ Yegül 1982: 7-31; Price 1984: 114; Schneider 1999: 66-9; Steskal forthcoming.

¹⁴ Yegül 1992: 250-313; Yegül 1986.

¹⁵ Steskal 2003: 227-39.

¹⁶ Steskal and Ladstätter forthcoming.

¹⁷ Keil 1926: 250-56.

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Fig. 1: Ephesus. City map (© Austrian Archaeological Institute).

Fig. 2: Vedius Gymnasium. Aerial view (© Austrian Archaeological Institute, Inv.-Nr.: A-W-OAI-EVG-00001).

Fig. 3: Vedius Gymnasium. Ground plan (© Austrian Archaeological Institute).

Fig. 4: So-called Kaisersaal with secondary *opus sectile* (© Austrian Archaeological Institute, Inv.-Nr.: A-W-OAI-EVG-01484).